

A Reconsideration of Psammetichus' Language Experiment and the Phrygian 'First Word'

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Among the most curious linguistic anecdotes preserved from antiquity is the story told by Herodotus (*Histories* 2.2) about the Egyptian pharaoh Psammetichus and his experiment to discover the world's oldest language. According to Herodotus, two newborn infants were raised in complete isolation, tended only by a shepherd and nourished by goats, while all human speech was forbidden in their presence. When the children were about two years old, they reportedly ran to the shepherd and uttered the word *bekos*, which was later identified as Phrygian for "bread." From this, the Egyptians concluded that the Phrygians were the most ancient people on earth. This famous episode has often been discussed as an early form of linguistic inquiry, even as a primitive experiment in developmental psychology. Yet the literal reading of the story contains an obvious difficulty: it is impossible that two infants, deprived of all speech, would spontaneously produce a real word from an existing foreign language. The episode, therefore, calls for reinterpretation not as a factual report but as a cultural myth built upon a misunderstanding of sound. The present study proposes that what the children actually uttered was not *bekos* but *behos*, an imitative sound reproducing the bleating of the goats that surrounded them. Isolated from human voices, the infants would naturally imitate the most frequent sound in their environment—the goats' *bah*, *baa* (cf. Romanian *behehe*). The resemblance between this sound and the Phrygian word *bekos* ("bread") could easily have led those who heard it to interpret it as a meaningful utterance. In this way, a simple imitation of animal sound was transformed into supposed linguistic evidence, giving rise to a legend about the primordial language of humankind.

References

Herodotus. *Histories*, Book II, 2.